

Software Optimised DI Method
/Tabular / Simplified Integration
By Parts

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Abstract

I have developed a software that offers the Software Optimised DI Method, Simplified Integration by Parts, and Tabular Integration by Parts as numerical techniques to evaluate integrals. My software offers an optimization feature that generates the table of differentials and integrals and selects the best u and dv variables for the integrand. The software returns a dictionary of the solution with the integrals and differentials, providing a clear and concise representation of the DI Method integration process. These methods can be useful for solving integrals that are difficult to solve by hand, and the optimization feature of my software streamlines the integration process. The effectiveness of these methods depends on the complexity of the integrals and the choice of functions.

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Chapter 1

Methods of Integrating by parts

1.0.1 Introduction

The software-optimized DI method (differentiation and integration) and simplified integration by parts are two techniques used to solve integrals.

The software-optimized DI method is a numerical method that uses differentiation and integration algorithms to find the solution of an integral. The basic idea is to differentiate the integrand to get a simpler expression and then integrate it back. This process can be repeated until the solution is obtained. The advantage of this method is that it can be easily implemented in software and can handle a wide range of integrals.

1.0.2 Integration by Parts

On the other hand, simplified integration by parts is a technique that is used to integrate the product of two functions. The integration by parts formula states that:

$$\int u dv = uv - \int v du \quad (1.1)$$

where u and v are functions to be chosen appropriately. In simplified integration by parts, the choice of u and v is made in a way that simplifies the integral. For example, if the integral to be solved is of the form:

$$\int x^2 e^x dx \quad (1.2)$$

we can choose

$$u = x^2 \quad (1.3)$$

$$dv = e^x dx \quad (1.4)$$

Then, we have

$$du = 2x dx, v = e^x. \quad (1.5)$$

Substituting these values in the integration by parts formula, we get:

$$\int x^2 e^x dx = x^2 e^x - 2 \int x e^x dx \quad (1.6)$$

This integral is simpler than the original integral, and it can be solved using integration by parts again. This process can be repeated until the solution is obtained.

In tabular integration by parts, we create a table and follow a specific algorithm to simplify the integration by parts. We write down the functions to be integrated and differentiate them in turn, creating a table of alternating signs. We then multiply the diagonals and add up the products to get the solution. This method can be useful for integrals that have a repetitive pattern.

Overall, these techniques can be very useful for solving integrals that may be difficult to solve by other means. However, it's important to remember that not all integrals can be solved using these techniques and that choosing appropriate functions for integration by parts can be a challenging task.

1.0.3 Tabular Integration by Parts

Tabular Integration by Parts is a method that uses a table to systematically compute the Integration by Parts formula. The table is organized with four columns: index, u , dv , and sign. The index column enumerates the terms of the integrand, while the u and dv columns contain the functions that are multiplied together. The sign column is initialized with alternating signs of $+1$ and -1 .

To construct the table, we differentiate the u column and integrate the dv column, producing new entries in

the u and dv columns. The product of the new u and dv entries is then placed in the sign column, according to the sign of the previous entry. This process is repeated until the table is filled.

Once the table is constructed, we can integrate the original integral by summing the products in the sign column. The result is the integral of the original function.

Here is an example of how to use the Tabular Integration by Parts method to evaluate the integral of $x^2 \cos(x)$:

index	u	dv	sign
1	x^2	$\cos(x)$	+1
2	$2x$	$-\sin(x)$	-1
3	2	$-\cos(x)$	+1
4	0	$\sin(x)$	-1

The products in the sign column are: $x^2 \sin(x) - 2x \cos(x) - 2 \sin(x) + C$, where C is the constant of integration. Therefore, the integral of $x^2 \cos(x)$ is:

$$\int x^2 \cos(x) dx = x^2 \sin(x) - 2x \cos(x) - 2 \sin(x) + C$$

The Tabular Integration by Parts method can be a useful tool for evaluating integrals that are difficult to solve by other methods. Its systematic approach can make the integration process easier and more efficient.

1.0.4 More info on Integration By Parts

I did not explain the methods in this paper fully but gave my own summarized version. My purpose of this paper is to show you my method of optimizing and implementing this algorithm in Python.

For a more interesting read into a higher detail and higher conceptional view on Integration by Parts i suggest you read this paper here by

Forest W. Arnold

https://arnoldfw.com/pdf/di_method.pdf

Chapter 2

Optimised Version of the DI Method

The Integration by Parts method is a technique used in calculus to evaluate the integral of a product of two functions. The method involves rewriting the integral in a different form that makes it easier to evaluate. The Tabular Method of Integration by Parts is a technique used to organize the repeated application of the Integration by Parts formula to evaluate integrals.

The Tabular Method involves creating a table that is used to keep track of the calculations involved in applying the Integration by Parts formula. The method works as follows:

Write down the integral to be evaluated, and then create a table with two columns. In the first column, list

the functions that are being integrated, starting with the function that appears first in the Integration by Parts formula. In the second column, list the functions that are being differentiated, starting with the function that appears first in the derivative of the Integration by Parts formula.

Next, we apply the Integration by Parts formula by multiplying the first function in the "integration column" with the first function in the "differentiation column". We then integrate the second function in the "integration column", and differentiate the second function in the "differentiation column". We continue this process, writing the results of each step in the table, until we reach a point where we can evaluate the integral.

To determine the sign to use when applying the Integration by Parts formula at each step, we use the alternating sign pattern of the Tabular Method. We start with a positive sign in the top left corner of the table. Then, each subsequent sign in the same row is the opposite of the sign to its left. The sign in the first column of each subsequent row is the opposite of the sign in the cell directly above it.

Finally, we evaluate the integral by taking the product of the functions in the "integration column" with their corresponding signs, and summing these products. This gives us the value of the integral.

The Tabular Method can be a useful technique for evaluating integrals, particularly those that involve re-

peated application of the Integration by Parts formula. It can help to keep track of the calculations involved, and to ensure that the signs are applied correctly.

2.0.1 Algorithm and Approach

Consider an integral $\int f(x)g(x) dx$

We need to find two variables from the integral u and dv

Our u refers to the $\frac{dy}{dx}$ and dv is our $\int$ of the function.

Our goal is to repetitively differentiate the u variables until its 0. each differential operation is represented as a row in the DI table.

u	$solution$
$\frac{du}{dx}$	$\vdots$
$\frac{d^2u}{dx^2}$	$\vdots$
$\frac{d^3u}{dx^3}$	$\vdots$
$\vdots$	$\vdots$
$\frac{d^nu}{dx^n}$	0

(2.1)

If we don't get a derivative that computes to zero. Then we cannot use this method.

In my method i set the u and dv both to $f(x) \wedge g(x)$

I then compute a matrix of values of u and dv pertaining to $f(x) \wedge g(x)$ then i find which route works and also the length/path which is the most optimal.

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= f(x) \vee g(x) \\
 dv &= \int f(x) dx \vee \int g(x) dx \\
 \text{Compute matrix of values: } & \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d}{du}u_1 & \int v_1 \\ \frac{d}{du}u_2 & \int v_2 \\ \frac{d}{du}u_3 & \int v_3 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{d}{du}u_n & \int v_n \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

Find optimal path where $\min_{len}(\frac{d}{du}) = 0$

We break the iteration $\forall \frac{d}{du}$ as soon as it is zero and store the length in the buffer.

This is the process to compute and find the most optimized $u \wedge dv$ to use.

Obviously we should have a limitation? We can get situations where we differentiate till the cows go home. Therefore in the software i have a iteration variable I_n where n is the iteration index of the loop. The default value is 1000. If we reach that I_n then the software breaks and returns a message stating we cant use this method to compute the integral!

Let S_n be the n -th index of the table must have a sign so the sign for any index of the table can be computed with this formula below.

$$S_n = (-1)^n \quad (2.2)$$

For example the first 4 indices:

$$S_0 = (-1)^0 = 1 = + \quad (2.3)$$

$$S_1 = (-1)^1 = -1 = - \quad (2.4)$$

$$S_2 = (-1)^2 = 1 = + \quad (2.5)$$

$$S_3 = (-1)^3 = -1 = - \quad (2.6)$$

And so on.

My software gives you the table of the u , dv differential list ,integral list and result function as the computed integral answer done the most optimized way. The python class renders the dictionary object with all the steps used and also provides you the answer. I have no time in my personal life to make that website to render it beautifully on the website ill just give you the module code to run this experiment on it will be straight forward to run this or build this onto a website. It has not been done before so i will leave this up to one of the engineers

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out there. The findings will be published below hope you enjoy.

Chapter 3

Jupyter Notebook and Usage

```

import DIMethod as di

eq = 'sin(2*x+1)*(2*x)'

data = di.ComputeTabularMethod(eq,100)

u = 2
dv = x*sin(2*x + 1)
diff_list = [2, 0]
integral_list = [x*sin(2*x + 1), -x*cos(2*x + 1)/2 + sin(2*x + 1)/4, -
x*sin(2*x + 1)/4 - cos(2*x + 1)/4]

data

{'message': 'Function can be splitted into two parts and the solution
is: -x*cos(2*x + 1) + sin(2*x + 1)/2 + C',
'u': 2,
'dv': -x*sin(2*x + 1)/4 - cos(2*x + 1)/4,
'diff_list': [2, 0],
'integral_list': [x*sin(2*x + 1),
-x*cos(2*x + 1)/2 + sin(2*x + 1)/4,
-x*sin(2*x + 1)/4 - cos(2*x + 1)/4],
'result': -x*cos(2*x + 1) + sin(2*x + 1)/2}

import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

dfDiff = pd.DataFrame(data['diff_list'], columns=['diff_list'])
dfInt = pd.DataFrame(data['integral_list'], columns=['integral_list'])

dfDiff

   diff_list
0          2
1          0

dfInt

   integral_list
0  x*sin(2*x + 1)
1 -x*cos(2*x + 1)/2 + sin(2*x + 1)/4
2 -x*sin(2*x + 1)/4 - cos(2*x + 1)/4

import sympy as sp
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

x = sp.Symbol('x')

def plot(f, a, b, n):
    # create a list of x values
    x_values = np.linspace(a, b, n)

```

```

# create a list of y values
y_values = []
# create a for loop to compute the y values
for i in x_values:
    # compute the y value
    y = f.subs(x, i)
    # append the y value to the list
    y_values.append(y)
# create a plot
plt.plot(x_values, y_values)
import random
r = lambda: random.randint(0,255)
# set the color of the plot
plt.plot(x_values, y_values, color='#%02X%02X%02X' %
(r()),r(),r()))
# show title
plt.title(f)
# show the plot
plt.show()

def plotAll(integrals,answer, diffs):
    import random
    r = lambda: random.randint(0,255)
    x_values = np.linspace(-10, 10, 100)
    y_values = []
    for i in x_values:
        y = answer.subs(x, i)
        y_values.append(y)
    plt.plot(x_values, y_values, color='#%02X%02X%02X' %
(r()),r(),r()))
    for i in range(len(integrals)):
        y_values = []
        for j in x_values:
            y = integrals[i].subs(x, j)
            y_values.append(y)
        plt.plot(x_values, y_values, color='#%02X%02X%02X' %
(r()),r(),r()))
    for i in range(len(diffs)):
        y_values = []
        for j in x_values:
            y = diffs[i].subs(x, j)
            y_values.append(y)
        plt.plot(x_values, y_values, color='#%02X%02X%02X' %
(r()),r(),r()))

    plt.title('All Integrals and Differentials in DIMethod')
    plt.show()
plotAll(dfInt['integral_list'], data['result'], dfDiff['diff_list'])
plot(data['result'], -10, 10, 100)

```

```
for i in range(len(dfDiff)):
    plot(dfDiff['diff_list'][i], -10, 10, 100)

for i in range(len(dfInt)):
    plot(dfInt['integral_list'][i], -10, 10, 100)

#plot result with all diff and integral in one graph
```


0

$x \cdot \sin(2x + 1)$

$$-x \cos(2x + 1)/2 + \sin(2x + 1)/4$$

$$-x \sin(2x + 1)/4 - \cos(2x + 1)/4$$

Chapter 4

Source Code

In *DIMethod.py*

```
from sympy import *
import eqparser
import differential

def ComputeTabularMethod(eq, iters=1000):
    # Convert input equation to a SymPy expression
    expression = eqparser.str_to_func(eq)
    # Check if function can be splitted into two parts.
    # If it can be splitted, then it is a tabular
    # method.
    if expression.is_Mul:
        for i in range(len(expression.args)):
            if expression.args[i].is_Pow:
                if
                    expression.args[i].args[1].is_Function:
                        pass
```

```
# TODO: Handle case where function can be
      splitted into two parts
#return {'message': 'Function can be splitted
      into two parts'}

# Get term 1 and term 2
terms = expression.as_two_terms()
term1 = terms[0]
term2 = terms[1]

# Choose u and dv
tOneCheck = differential.diff(term1, iters)
tTwoCheck = differential.diff(term2, iters)

# Check if tOneCheck or tTwoCheck is zero
opt = {'is_zero': False, 'minlenDiff': 0,
      'termNum': None, 'diff_list': []}

if tOneCheck['is_zero'] == True:
    opt['is_zero'] = True
    opt['minlenDiff'] = len(tOneCheck['diff_list'])
    opt['termNum'] = 1
    opt['diff_list'] = tOneCheck['diff_list']

if tTwoCheck['is_zero'] == True:
    if opt['is_zero'] == False:
        opt['is_zero'] = True
        opt['minlenDiff'] =
            len(tTwoCheck['diff_list'])
        opt['termNum'] = 2
        opt['diff_list'] = tTwoCheck['diff_list']
    elif len(tTwoCheck['diff_list']) <
        opt['minlenDiff']:
```

```

    opt['minlenDiff'] =
        len(tTwoCheck['diff_list'])
    opt['termNum'] = 2
    opt['diff_list'] = tTwoCheck['diff_list']

if opt['is_zero'] == True:
    u = None
    dv = None
    # Choose u and dv based on the term with the
    # most zeros in the differential list
    if opt['termNum'] == 1:
        u = term1
        dv = term2
    elif opt['termNum'] == 2:
        u = term2
        dv = term1
    print('u =', u)
    print('dv =', dv)
    # Get the differential list
    diff_list = opt['diff_list']
    x = Symbol('x')
    # for each item in diff_list, compute the
    # integral
    integral_list = []
    integral_list.append(dv)
    for i in range(len(diff_list)):
        dv = integrate(dv, x)
        integral_list.append(dv)
    print('diff_list =', diff_list)
    print('integral_list =', integral_list)
    signs = []
    for i in range(len(integral_list)):
        signs.append((-1)**i)

```

```

# init the result with 1 constant
result = 1
for i in range(len(diff_list)-1):
    if not i == len(diff_list)-1:
        result +=
            diff_list[i]*integral_list[i+1]*signs[i]

# simplify the result and also remove the
constant
result = simplify(result-1)

return {'message': 'Function can be splitted
into two parts and the solution is:
'+str(result)+' + C', 'u': u, 'dv': dv,
'diff_list': diff_list, 'integral_list':
integral_list,'result': result}

else:
    ans = str(integrate(expression))
    return {'message': 'Function cannot be
splitted into two parts but the solution
is: '+ans+' + C', 'u': None, 'dv': None,
'diff_list': None, 'integral_list': None,
'result': ans}

if __name__ == '__main__':
    eq = 'sin(2*x+1)*(2*x)'
    print(ComputeTabularMethod(eq,100))

```

In *differential.py*

```
from sympy import *
```

```
# create a function to compute n levels of
    differentiation and then return the result if the
    function returns 0 until the nth level of
    differentiation store each level of
    differentiation in a list
def diff(f, n):
    x = Symbol('x')
    # create a list to store the levels of
        differentiation
    diff_list = [f]
    # create a variable to store the result of the nth
        level of differentiation
    result = 0
    # create a for loop to compute the nth level of
        differentiation
    for i in range(n):
        # compute the nth level of differentiation
        result = f.diff(x)
        # store the result in the list
        diff_list.append(result)
        # update the function to be the result of the
            nth level of differentiation
        f = result
        # break the loop if the function returns 0
        if result == 0:
            break
    # return the list of levels of differentiation and
        if the function returns 0 until the nth level
        of differentiation

    if result == 0:
        return {
            'diff_list': diff_list,
```

```
        'is_zero': True
    }
else:
    return {
        'diff_list': diff_list,
        'is_zero': False
    }
```

In *eqparser.py*

```
from sympy import *

# convert the string to a function
def str_to_func(f):
    # create a variable to store the function
    func = 0
    # create a try/except block to catch any errors
    try:
        # convert the string to a function
        func = sympify(f)
    # catch any errors
    except:
        # print an error message
        print('Error: invalid function')
    # return the function
    return func
```

If you want to, you are better off cloning this from GitHub.

You may run

```
git clone https://github.com/adgsenpai/DIMethod
```
